

ШУМЕНСКИ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ “ЕПИСКОП КОНСТАНТИН ПРЕСЛАВСКИ”

SHOUMEN UNIVERSITY “BISHOP KONSTANTIN PRES LAVSKY”

НАУЧНИ ТРУДОВЕ

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИ КОЛЕЖ, ДОБРИЧ

ТОМ V

PROCEEDINGS

PEDAGOGICAL COLLEGE, DOBRICH

VOLUME V

Университетско издателство
”Епископ Константин Преславски”

ПЛЕНАРНИ ДОКЛАДИ

MATHEMATICS EDUCATION AND POLITICS – THE POLITICS OF MATHEMATICS EDUCATION

Christine Keitel,
Freie University Berlin

Introduction: Mathematics, knowledge and political power

To characterize the actual political and social situation in mathematics education around the world, in particular in most of the rich countries, one could state that the commercial textbook ‘business’ community controls the materials available to teachers to an extent that teachers are rather slaves of the textbook than autonomous and enlightened users; and that assessment still is primarily and predominantly a mechanism for selecting the mathematical elite only instead to provide a profound mathematics education to all. The few promising developments in mathematics education could be seen in the increasing availability of personal technology, in the growth of the vocational education sector, in the growth of the informal sector through web-access, and – my big hope – in the increasing professionalization of mathematics teacher associations in many countries and the growth of equal and fair collaborative research within the mathematics education community.

In my view the challenge for all of us within mathematics education is how to support developments from within our own - often highly politicised - educational contexts, and with our own limited resources to mainly focus on:

- Developing social and political dimensions of mathematics education academically and as a serious field of empirical investigation and theoretical study.

- Analysing and questioning associations, organizations, and conferences of mathematics education socially and politically.

These main questions aim at investigations on how we could further develop and ensure the autonomy and professionalization of mathematics educators and mathematics teachers and their active role in their associations or organizations although there have been raised many contradictory proposals. Our colleague Alan Bishop had put the question forward provocatively: "Do we speak for ourselves and are we really autonomous in our professional and organisational decisions? Who are those and for whom do they speak that are driving policy in mathematics education?"

The following issues and concerns address problems of mathematics education research and policy practice that could serve as a guideline for a broad discussion:

- Social and political views about mathematics and mathematics education: Is mathematics really for All?
- Social justice and mathematics education: Dream-team or Nightmare?
- Social and political conflicts by poverty, violence and instability: What has math education to offer and contribute against these?

- Challenges and perils of globalisation in international collaboration: Who gets a fair deal?
- Contradictory demands and measures for new qualities of mathematics and mathematics education research: Who determines what concerns mathematics education and is dealt with in mathematics education research?

1. Mathematics as means of political power

Mathematics is perceived today as one of the most powerful social means for planning, optimizing, steering, representing and communicating social affairs created by mankind. And by the development of modern information and communication technologies based on mathematics, this social impact of mathematics came to full political power: Mathematics is now universally used in all domains of society, and there is nearly no political decision-making process, in which mathematics is not used as the “rational” argument and the “objective base” that is considered as replacing political judgements and power relations: mathematics as objective truth and political-free. For the ordinary citizen today, in contrast to public political propaganda, it becomes increasingly difficult and sometimes impossible to follow developments of mathematics, in particular mathematical applications with ICT, and to evaluate their social use appropriately, because specialisation and segmentation of mathematical applications often are extremely hard to understand. The principal insight into their necessity and a basic acknowledgement of their importance in general are often confronted by a complete lack of knowledge of concrete examples of their impact, not to speak about alternatives. However, competencies to evaluate mathematical applications and ICT, and the possible usefulness or its problematic effects, now seem to be a necessary precondition for any political executive and for real democratic participation of citizens. The new challenge is to determine what kind of knowledge and meta-knowledge in a mathematised society is needed and how to gain the necessary constituents.

The development of competencies for decision-making under conditions that include the coding and processing of knowledge by means of systems of symbols (e.g. book-keeping, planning models, calculation of investment or pensions, quality control, theories of risks, IT in banking etc.) and their complete mathematisation, is not only an actual problem. The history offers numerous examples for the fact that similar problems arose at

various times, although in historically specific forms and with historically specific solutions. In particular, examples of historically radical breaks in the organisation of decision-making could be referred to, i.e. examples of developments, in which the mutual effect of changes of knowledge systems and innovations in the technology of using information have questioned traditional mechanisms of decision-making as well in the educational and social policy as in policy for scientific development, which in long terms have been replaced by new forms. One example with particularly radical consequences is the linking of controllable empirical research and newly developed forms of representations of mathematical theories during the raise of classical sciences in the 16th and 17th century, another example is the raise of modern physics at the beginning of 20th century, in which - like in the first example - not only the changes immanent to scientific research and practice were of importance, but the accompanying complete revision of decision-making processes about the production, the use and evaluation of social and scientific knowledge. In the first case, the consequence was the development of a new organisation of autonomous bodies or systems of sciences, in the second it was the raise of modern, independent and rather autonomous institutions for scientific research only. Both examples are not singular cases. (Damerow & Lefèvre 1981; Hoyrup & Damerow 2001; Keitel 2007, Renn 2002)

Studies in the history and philosophy of sciences show that changes of the forms of symbolising and processing of information usually had mutual effects on social organisations and led to new structures of scientific knowledge. Together with the change of structures of knowledge, different characteristic styles of thinking and in particular worldviews were developed, which also effected fundamental changes in the process of political decision-making on general social goals, and on means and measures to pursue them, accompanied by changes in the allocation of resources in a society.

Since the beginning of social organisation, social knowledge of exposing, exchanging, storing and controlling information in either ritualised or symbolized (formalised) way was needed, therefore developed and used, in particular information that is closely related to production, distribution and exchange of goods and organisation of labour. This is assumed as one of the origins of mathematics: early concepts of number and number operations, concepts of time and space, have been invented as means for governance and administration in response to social needs. Mathematics served early on as a distinctive tool for problem solving in social practices and as means of social power. Control of these social practices and the transmission of the necessary knowledge to the responsible agents were often secured by direct participation in social activities and direct oral communication among the members. Ritualised procedures of storing and using information have been developed since Neolithic revolution, during the transition to agriculture and permanent living sites, which e.g. demanded planning the cycles of the year.

The urban revolution and the existence of stratified societies with a strong division of labour induced symbolical storage and control of social practices by information systems based on mathematics, which were bound to domain-specific systems of symbols with conventional meaning: Mathematics employed as a technique and a useful and necessary tool and the governing class disposed of mathematics as an additional instrument of securing and extending its political power and authority. The earliest documents available are the clay tablets from Mesopotamia (Uruk 3000 BC), in which mathematics appears as necessary and useful tool for solving problems of agriculture and economic administration – “bookkeeping” of production and distribution of goods in a highly hierarchically structured slavery based society (Nissen et al. 1990, Høyrup & Damerow 2001, Damerow, 2007).

A new, most consequential perspective of mathematics emerged in Ancient Greece: For the Greek mathematics was detached from the needs of managing ordinary daily life as from the necessity of gaining their living. Instead, by scientific search for fundamental, clearly hierarchically ordered bases, creating connections and elements of a systemic characterisation of existing formal mathematical problem solving techniques and devices, independent of any specific practical intention, they reformulated mathematics as a scientific system and philosophy, a (Platonic) ideal theory to be further discovered and constructed by human theoretical thinking and reasoning, not by doing or solving practical problems. This distinction between mathematics as the queen, as a science of formal systems by introducing a structure and defining mathematical thinking as logical reasoning from axioms to concepts and theorems to proofs, in opposition to a view of mathematics as a simple technique or (problem solving) tool, which is only and simply used: mathematics as the servant, is ascribed to Greek scholars (Snell, 1948).

Being able to think mathematically was a sign of those who had political power. By viewing mathematics as the structure underlying the construction of the cosmos and *number* as the basis of the universe and emphasizing a hermetical character of the mathematical community, the ground was laid for the high esteem of mathematics as a segregation means of political and social power.

Over the centuries, the traces of structuring the world by human rational activity became more numerous, appropriate dealing with it, more imposing. There were several fields in which the mathematisation of the real world and of social life advanced more remarkably, among these notably architecture, military development in both, fortification and armament, mining industry, milling and water-regulation, surveying, and before all, manufacturing and trade. The extension of trade from local business to far distances exchange prompted the emergence of banking, and for the functioning of this an unambiguous form of clear and universal regulation was needed: the system of book-keeping was invented. In none of these systems mathematical devices were

without political intention and power relations, mathematical structures determined whole fields of social practices, which are working until present days. (Damerow et al. 1974)

2. Social needs for mathematics and mathematics education in the course of history

The achievements of the 15th to 19th century entailed an explosion of trades, crafts, manufacturing and industrial activities with an impressive diversity, ingenuity, and craftsmanship developed and required in numerous professions. The ability of a greater part of the population to appropriately dealing with fundamental systems of symbols like writing and calculating became a precondition for the functioning of societies: Elementary (mathematics) education and training – although clearly restricted to defined needs - was established as reaction to social demands, either prior or during vocational training and various professional practices. Parallel to upcoming educational institutions and in concert with them, mass production for unlimited reproduction of knowledge enabled and asked for standardisation and canonical bodies and representations of knowledge. A reflection and restructuring of existing knowledge on a higher level was demanded: Meta-knowledge had to be developed that offered standards of knowledge and their canonical representations for educational purposes; at the same time meta-knowledge as orienting knowledge became an immanent condition for developing new systems of knowledge, in particular for sciences like mathematics that were perceived to a greater part as independent of immediate practical purposes.

In the 19th century, the competition between the bigger European states, inspired by a strong and fateful ideology of national superiority and ambition, drew attention to “knowledge as power”, making public education a central interest of governments. Industrialisation was accompanied by an increasing autonomy of systems of scientific and practical knowledge. To be a mathematician, somebody who does mathematics and nothing else, emerged as a new profession. Mathematics was conceived as an autonomous subject domain, without immediate practical use in other domains, and mathematicians worked as scholars at university or as high-level school teachers.

As in sciences, specialization and professionalization of experts were requirements in all branches of economy, as in social services and administration. Constructing and creating new knowledge became a precondition for the material reproduction of society, not a consequence. Specialisation was a condition for creating new knowledge, but at the same time bore the risk of disintegrating more comprising systems of knowledge and making integration in a wider context difficult. Partial knowledge must be generalised and incorporated on a level of meta-knowledge.

3. Mathematics education as a public need and task

In the 19th century in many countries, public and state controlled two partite school systems were created: higher education as mind forming for an elite, elementary education to transmit skills and working behaviour for the majority, the future working class. Humboldt’s notion of “Bildung” comprised learning as universal as ever possible with strong emphasise on humanities: Philosophy, history, literature, art, music, but for purposes of enlightenment with an even stronger emphasis on mathematics and sciences. The ideal was the completely cultivated, best educated human being, and “Bildung” was not a process, an attitude and a path as much as an accomplishment. And that was to be conveyed by means of public education, at schools and at universities. Mathematics became subject in higher education institution for the elite and governing class because of its formal educational qualities, e.g. educating the mind independent of a direct utilitarian perspective, and fostering general attitudes to support the scientific and science-driven technological development. In the elementary or general school for workers and farmers, only arithmetic teaching in a utilitarian sense was offered: to secure the necessary skills for the labour force, to secure acceptance of formal rules and formal procedures set up by others. A clear restriction was set up: Mathematics education for the few was strictly separated from the skill training for the majority, this corresponded to a separation of mathematics education as an art and science in contrast to mathematics education as a technique, scientific knowledge and conceptual thinking versus technical, algorithmic, machine-like acting.

4. Mathematics education for All? The failure of a social ambition

In the 19th and 20th century, mathematics became the driving force for almost all scientific and technological developments: mathematical and scientific models and their transformation into technology had large impact not only on natural and social sciences and economics but also on all activities in the social, professional and daily life. This impact increased rapidly by the development of the new information and communication technologies (ICT) based on mathematics, which radically changed the social organisation of labour and our perceptions of knowledge or technique to an extent that is not yet fully explored.

On the one side, mathematics as a human activity in a social environment is determined by social structures, hence it is not interest-free or politically neutral. On the other side, the continuous application of mathematical models, viewed as universal problem solving procedures, provide not only descriptions and predictions of social actions, but also prescriptions: The increasing social use of mathematics makes mathematical methods and ways of argumentation to quasi-natural social rules and constraints, and creates a mathematised social order effective in social organisations, hierarchical institutions like bureaucracy, administration, management of production and distribution, institutions of law and military etc. Social and political decisions are turned into facts, constraints or prescriptions that individual and collective human behaviour have to follow.

New perspectives of the social role of (mathematical) knowledge and general education were developed that partly gained political acceptance and support: “Mathematics education for All“ and “Mathematical Literacy”. The concepts were differently substantiated and received different interpretations and supporters: The New Math movement had started to introduce mathematics for all by a formally unified, universally applicable body of theoretical knowledge of modern mathematics exposed to all, but had to be revisited and discarded as a solution. Intensive work in curriculum development created a wide range of different and more and more comprehensive approaches combining new research results in related disciplines like psychology, sociology, and education and developed this vision further (Howson, Keitel, Kilpatrick 1981, Sierpiska & Kilpatrick 1998). A variety of conceptions promised to describe the socially necessary knowledge in a more substantiated form and to integrate scientific mathematical practices and common vocational or professional practices and their craft knowledge, or conceptual and procedural knowledge, or mathematical modelling and application.

However, the most radical development within and outside of mathematics as a discipline was caused by the invention of electronic media and the new possibility of data-processing and control. The immediate consequence, based on the integration of human-mental and sensory-information processing techniques within machines, is the creation of technologies which take over human information processes and independently determine social organisation. This new development is called globalisation of knowledge: the technological integration of new representation forms and the distribution of knowledge in a global net of knowledge represent the greatest challenge for a restructuring of political power and decision making processes about the way, in which information is gained and used, available to anybody everywhere with access to the internet.

Information and communication technologies are the fundament for communication which is an essential aspect of globalisation: access to and exchange of information and knowledge from anywhere in the world, quickly and cheaply. On the one hand, that leads to a general acknowledgement of cultural diversity, but on the other hand also to universalisation and domination by certain languages and cultural positions - e.g. the English language and Euro-American or Western belief systems, encompassing a variety of knowledge traditions and knowledge systems.

The social role and impact of mathematics has dramatically changed by the development of modern information technologies based on mathematics. Mathematics is ascribed a new utility value, which has never before been so strongly indubitable as it is now. Illustrating examples for new technological and most effective applications of mathematical methods are numerous, e.g.: Computer-based simulations are applied in most different areas like modelling of climate changes, crash tests, chemical reaction kinetics by building process-oriented technical machines, dynamical system models in macroeconomics and biology.

Software packages allow the most complex calculation processes for many applications in forms of black boxes, like statistical processes in quality control, research on market and products, risk theories for portefeuille-management in assurance companies, computer based algebra systems and software for modelling in sciences and engineering. Mathematics as the basis of many technologies is effective although only invisibly, i.e. as theoretical base of formal language in informatics, as fundament of coding algorithms for industrial robots or in the daily used scanners, mobile phones, cash corners or electronic cashiers. New technologies in return have feedback with great impact on mathematics as a discipline itself. Besides traditional applied mathematics new directions combined applied sciences with experimental procedures like techno-mathematics, industrial mathematics, theory of algorithms.

New procedures in some application areas are celebrated not only as new means to ends or a refined methodological repertoire, but furthermore as a new paradigm: In contrast to classical applied mathematics, which was oriented towards and restricted to the representation of mathematical structures of a reality existing completely independent of any subjective intention, new forms of applications do not hide the fact that interests and intentions always guide the construction of a model, as well as specific goals and convictions. The theoretical poverty of such models is interpreted as advantage, as no comprehensive theories of the object have to be presupposed, by some the new paradigm is celebrated as humanisation of modelling and mathematics.

Mathematics and information technology not only provide descriptions and explanations of existing reality, but they also *create* new reality: As a basis of social technologies like arithmetical models for election modes, taxation models, calculation of interests and investment, calculation of costs and pensions etc., mathematical models are transformed into reality, establish and institutionalise a new kind of reality. This process can be reconstructed and analysed as the development of implicit mathematics: Patterns of social acting and formal structures are transformed via formal languages into algorithms or mathematical models which can be rectified and objectified as social technologies. In models of macro-economy, translations of an ideology into mathematical concepts can be identified, which by enrichment with subtle economical terminology and by internal consistency of the mathematical representation suggest not only progress, but existence as a natural law. In such a way, mathematisations also can be established as unconscious cultural forms and rites and as a kind of language that create a milieu for thoughts, which further creates unquestioned constraints and restrictions of consciousness (Keitel, Kotzmann, Skovsmose 1993; vgl auch Davis & Hersh 1986, Davis 1989.).

Such results of applications of mathematics are often encountered in communication situations mainly shaped by conflicting interests where they serve to justify opinions and to stabilise attitudes. Graphical representations of information e.g. are excellently structured, provide sufficient overview and relative

universality of readability, but are also appropriate means for accentuation guiding the perception into wrong directions. In such communication processes the possibilities for interaction between interpreters are usually restricted. Even neglecting the fact that credibility is often depending on the prestige of the participants, the prestige of mathematics as such often serves to suggest objectivity and objective goals and intentions. Thus the regulation and democratic control of actual and future research, development and application processes of mathematics and mathematics education demand a specific competence and knowledge as a basis of decision making on the side of the politicians and new knowledge for evaluation and democratic control on the side of the citizens.

5. Mathematical Literacy for political power and critical citizenship

The pervasiveness of economic thinking and interests have successively created so high a pressure of economic orientation that educational aims and the subject matter are marginalized unless they prove justification in terms of economic interest (Woodrow, 2003). New notions like “Mathematical Proficiency, or Competency or Literacy”, “Educational Standards” and “Benchmarks” are expressions of such economic interests. They are a major concern of politicians but also a pressure for educational researchers and practitioners. They are the key issues in the recent political debates and disputes about mathematics education, which broadened after the release of international comparative studies like TIMSS and PISA and their ranking of test results. Proclaiming that the PISA tests are based on “definitions of mathematical literacy” that are underpinned by fundamental and widely accepted educational research results, and that it is absolutely unproblematic to test such kind of competencies or proficiencies on a global scale to rank countries’ performances, produced strange and urgent political measures to be taken in some of the countries that did not perform well, called for by the alarmed public and the medias. Results of tests like PISA are used as reference and base for decisions in educational policy, in particular in cases when they show that only a small part of the tested students or adults have reached a higher level of competencies in the international comparison.

The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) claims for its test of Mathematical Literacy, that those competencies of young adolescents are measured, which enable them to participate in democratic decision-making processes: „Mathematical Literacy is the capacity to identify, to understand and to engage in mathematics and make well-founded judgements about the role that mathematics plays, as needed for an individual’s current and future life, occupational life, social life with peers and relatives, and life as a constructive, concerned and reflective citizen“ (OECD 2000, 50)

As this definition clearly demonstrates, each attempt to define Mathematical Literacy is confronted with the problem that this can not be done exclusively in terms of mathematical knowledge: To understand mathematised contexts or mathematical applications and to competently use mathematics in contexts goes beyond mathematical knowledge. An early and first research study to explore such cross-curricular competencies by investigating the ways how mathematics is used in a social-political practice had unexpected and surprising results (Damerow et al. 1974).

Conflicting conceptions of Mathematical Literacy are numerous, although not always the conflict is recognised: Jablonka (Jablonka 2003) analysed what research on Mathematical Literacy can and cannot do. She investigated different perspectives on Mathematical Literacy and showed that these perspectives always considerably vary with the values and rationales of the stakeholders who promote them. The central argument underlying each of her investigations is that it is not possible to promote a conception of Mathematical Literacy without at the same time – implicitly or explicitly – promoting a particular social practice of mathematics: be it the practice of mathematicians, of scientists, of economists, of professional practices outside science and mathematics etc. She argues that Mathematical Literacy focussing on citizenship in particular refers to the possibility or need of critically evaluating most important issues of the surrounding society or culture of the students – a society and culture that are very much shaped by practices involving mathematics. In her conclusion, she emphasises that the ability to understand and to evaluate different practices of mathematics and the values behind has to be a component of Mathematical Literacy.

Mathematical Literacy must be understood as functional in relation to pedagogical postulates. But by reducing the concept of Mathematical Literacy to the descriptions of the process of its measurement cannot be justified, while conclusions of these comparisons mostly are formulated in terms of daily language or connected with highly demanding and complex meanings and connotations of the concepts.

The demands and threats of the *Knowledge Society* are referred to in most political declarations and justifications for educational policy. From an international or global point of view, this includes to investigate what approaches towards knowledge perceptions are taken in different countries, at the levels of policy and of practice; what are the most important knowledge conflicts at various social levels, and in particular in the educational systems, e.g. clashes between students’ personal knowledge and the knowledge presented by teachers, between knowledge systems, between ‘modern/popular’ cultures and traditional cultures, between teachers’ and students’ views (Clarke, Keitel & Shimizu 2006); and on the more general level, e.g. how are global technologies – especially the World-Wide-Web, television and print media – used to promote or diminish diversity, or what effects of inequality are reproduced.

The question how mathematics is perceived and used in political debates and decision-making processes, in particular in decisions that concern mathematics education, is a necessary complement to be studied. Case

studies to investigate which connections are established between results of comparative studies on mathematical competencies and the attributions of causes and effects deduced from them in the public debate are a very promising beginning. To collect and analyse which criteria for political decisions and which forms of decision-making processes are defined and stated, which kind of controlling mechanisms to secure quality is foreseen or used and on what the credibility of results is based, in particular in the media, is highly needed. We try to reconstruct the origin and history of such studies and confront criteria and decisions for selecting the participating institutions and experts, contrast the official publications of national and international projects and the reconstruction of views and conceptions held by participating experts in interviews. The history of the social reception of these studies is to be interpreted in the light of conflicts of interests and different interest groups. An analysis of published statements of all stakeholders in political decision-making processes and of representatives of interest groups in industry and economy has been started, complemented by interviews with teachers, mathematicians and experts in the ICT-area. Here I would like to follow an approach that is used by Leone Burton in her very much enlightening analyses of mathematicians views about mathematics (Burton 2003). The interpretations of these statements in the light of the factual political interests have to be re-analysed on the base of the historical accounts of mathematics as means of social power and of the actual account of modern mathematics as a scientific discipline and technology provider. The close relationship between mathematics and policy leads hopefully to a debate about what and how much mathematics is needed to educate or create politically aware, well informed and critical citizens for a democratic society.

REFERENCES

1. **Bishop**, A. Mathematical Power to the people. In: Harvard Educational Review, Vol. 60, No. 3, August 1990, p. 357-369
2. **Burton**, L. Mathematicians as Enquirers. Learning about Learning Mathematics, Dordrecht, Kluwer, 2003
3. **Clarke**, D., C. Keitel, Y. Shimizu, (eds.) Mathematics classrooms in 12 countries: The insiders' perspectives. LPS-series No. 1, Rotterdam, Sense, 2006
4. **Damerow**, P., U. Elwitz, C. Keitel, J. Zimmer. Elementarmathematik: Lernen für die Praxis? Ein exemplarischer Versuch der Bestimmung fachübergreifender Curriculumziele (Elementary mathematics: Learning for practice? An exemplary attempt to determine cross-curricular goals in mathematics), Stuttgart, Klett, 1974
5. **Damerow**, P., W. Lefèvre (eds) Rechenstein, Experiment, Sprache. Historische Fallstudien zur Entstehung der exakten Wissenschaften, Stuttgart, Klett-Cotta, 1981
6. **Davis**, P. Applied Mathematics as Social Contract. In: C. Keitel et. al. (eds.) Mathematics, Education and Society, Unesco Document Series No. 35, Paris, Unesco, 1989, p. 24-28
7. **Ernest**, P. Forms of Knowledge in Mathematics and Mathematics Education: Philosophical and Rhetorical Perspectives. Educational Studies in Mathematics, 1999, p. 38 (1-3), 67-83
8. **Gellert**, U., E. Jablonka, C. Keitel. Mathematical Literacy and Common Sense in Mathematics Education". In: B. Atweh et al. (Eds.) Sociocultural Aspects of Mathematics Education, New York, Lawrence Erlbaum, 2001, p. 57-73
9. **Howson**, G. A., C. Keitel, J. Kilpatrick. Curriculum development in mathematics. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 1981
10. **Jablonka**, E. Mathematical Literacy. In: Bishop, A., Clements, K., Keitel, C., Kilpatrick, J., Leung, F. (eds) Second International Handbook of Mathematics Education. Dordrecht, Kluwer, 2003, p. 77-104
11. **Keitel**, C., K. Ruthven (eds.). Learning from computers: Mathematics education and technology . Berlin, Springer, 1993
12. **Keitel**, C., E. Kotzmann, O. Skovsmose. Beyond the tunnel vision: Analysing the relationship between mathematics education, society and technology. In C. Keitel & K. Ruthven (eds.), Learning from computers: Mathematics education and technology . Berlin, Springer, 1993, p. 242-279
13. **Nissen**, H., P. Damerow, R. K. Englund. Frühe Schrift und Techniken der Wirtschaftsverwaltung im Vorderen Orient: Informationsspeicherung und -verarbeitung vor 5000 Jahren [Early writing and technologies of the management and administration of economics in the Near East: Information storing and processing 5000 years ago]. Bad Salzdetfurth, Germany, Franzbecker, 1990
14. OECD (eds.) Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). Paris, OECD, 2000
15. **Renn**, J. Wissenschaft als Lebensorientierung – eine Erfolgsgeschichte? Preprint 224, Berlin, Max-Planck-Institut für Wissenschaftsgeschichte, 2002
16. **Sierpiska**, A., J. Kilpatrick (eds.). Mathematics Education as a Research Domain, A Search for Identity. Dordrecht: Kluwer, 1998
17. **Woodrow**, D. Mathematics, mathematics education and economic conditions. In: A. Bishop, K. Clements, C. Keitel, J. Kilpatrick, F. Leung (eds.). Second International Handbook of Mathematics Education. Dordrecht, Kluwer, 2003, p. 11-32
